
AN ENDPOINT FUNCTIONAL CONTINUOUS UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

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Abstract: Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ be continuous 1-Schauder frames for a Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we show that

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(\omega_\beta)|}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)|}.$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_f : \mathcal{X} \ni x &\mapsto \theta_f x \in \mathcal{L}^1(\Omega, \mu); & \theta_f x : \Omega \ni \alpha &\mapsto (\theta_f x)(\alpha) := f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}, \\ \theta_g : \mathcal{X} \ni x &\mapsto \theta_g x \in \mathcal{L}^1(\Delta, \nu); & \theta_g x : \Delta \ni \beta &\mapsto (\theta_g x)(\beta) := g_\beta(x) \in \mathbb{K}. \end{aligned}$$

This solves a problem asked by K. M. Krishna in the paper ‘Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle’ [*arXiv:2308.00312v1*].

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1. INTRODUCTION

Given a collection $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ in a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} over \mathbb{K} (\mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C}), let

$$\theta_\tau : \mathcal{H} \ni h \mapsto \theta_\tau h := (\langle h, \tau_j \rangle)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n.$$

Following is the most general form of discrete uncertainty principle for finite dimensional Hilbert spaces.

Theorem 1.1. (*Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani Uncertainty Principle*) [1, 2, 5] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two Parseval frames for a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then*

$$\left(\frac{\|\theta_\tau h\|_0 + \|\theta_\omega h\|_0}{2} \right)^2 \geq \|\theta_\tau h\|_0 \|\theta_\omega h\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|^2}, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}.$$

Recently, Theorem 1.1 has been greatly improved to continuous families in Banach spaces (even infinite dimensions). To state the result, we need a notion.

Definition 1.2. [3] *Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space. Let $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in a Banach space \mathcal{X} and $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in \mathcal{X}^* . The pair $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ is said to be a **continuous p -Schauder frame** for \mathcal{X} ($1 < p < \infty$) if the following holds.*

- (i) *For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.*

(ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\|^p = \int_{\Omega} |f_{\alpha}(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha).$$

(iii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_{\alpha}(x)\tau_{\alpha} \in \mathcal{X}$ is weakly measurable.

(iv) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$x = \int_{\Omega} f_{\alpha}(x)\tau_{\alpha} d\mu(\alpha),$$

where the integral is weak integral.

Note that condition (i) in Definition 1.2 says that the map

$$\theta_f : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \theta_f x \in \mathcal{L}^p(\Omega, \mu); \quad \theta_f x : \Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto (\theta_f x)(\alpha) := f_{\alpha}(x) \in \mathbb{K}$$

is a linear isometry.

Theorem 1.3. (Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle) [3] Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $(\{f_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ be continuous p -Schauder frames for a Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})|}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})|},$$

where q is the conjugate index of p .

Corollary 1.4. (Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani Uncertainty Principle) [4] Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m)$ be p -Schauder frames for a finite dimensional Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have

$$\|\theta_f x\|_0^{\frac{1}{p}} \|\theta_g x\|_0^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(\omega_k)|} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\theta_g x\|_0^{\frac{1}{p}} \|\theta_f x\|_0^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g_k(\tau_j)|},$$

where q is the conjugate index of p .

In paper [3], it is asked that whether we have version of Theorem 1.3 for $p = 1$ and $p = \infty$. In this paper, we solve the problem for $p = 1$.

2. FUNCTIONAL CONTINUOUS UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE FOR CONTINUOUS 1-SCHAUDER FRAMES

We clearly have the following definition from Definition 1.2.

Definition 2.1. Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space. Let $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in a Banach space \mathcal{X} and $\{f_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in \mathcal{X}^* . The pair $(\{f_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ is said to be a **continuous 1-Schauder frame** for \mathcal{X} if the following holds.

- (i) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_{\alpha}(x) \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.
- (ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\| = \int_{\Omega} |f_{\alpha}(x)| d\mu(\alpha).$$

- (iii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_{\alpha}(x)\tau_{\alpha} \in \mathcal{X}$ is weakly measurable.

(iv) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$x = \int_{\Omega} f_{\alpha}(x) \tau_{\alpha} d\mu(\alpha),$$

where the integral is weak integral.

We note that condition (i) in Definition 2.1 says that the map

$$\theta_f : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \theta_f x \in \mathcal{L}^1(\Omega, \mu); \quad \theta_f x : \Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto (\theta_f x)(\alpha) := f_{\alpha}(x) \in \mathbb{K}$$

is a linear isometry.

Theorem 2.2. (Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle for Continuous 1-Schauder Frames) Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $(\{f_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ be continuous 1-Schauder frames for a Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})|}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})|}.$$

In particular,

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \geq \frac{1}{\left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)}$$

and

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) + \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})|} + \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})|}.$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$. First using θ_f is an isometry and later using θ_g is an isometry, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|x\| &= \|\theta_f x\| = \int_{\Omega} |f_{\alpha}(x)| d\mu(\alpha) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x)| d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\int_{\Delta} g_{\beta}(x) \omega_{\beta} d\nu(\beta) \right) \right| d\mu(\alpha) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| \int_{\Delta} g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta}) d\nu(\beta) \right| d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta}) d\nu(\beta) \right| d\mu(\alpha) \leq \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)| d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)| d\nu(\beta) \\ &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \|\theta_g x\| = \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \|x\|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(\omega_\beta)|} \leq \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)).$$

On the other way, first using θ_g is an isometry and θ_f is an isometry, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|x\| &= \|\theta_g x\| = \int_{\Delta} |g_\beta(x)| d\nu(\beta) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_\beta(x)| d\nu(\beta) \\ &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| g_\beta \left(\int_{\Omega} f_\alpha(x) \tau_\alpha d\mu(\alpha) \right) \right| d\nu(\beta) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| \int_{\Omega} f_\alpha(x) g_\beta(\tau_\alpha) d\mu(\alpha) \right| d\nu(\beta) \\ &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} f_\alpha(x) g_\beta(\tau_\alpha) d\mu(\alpha) \right| d\nu(\beta) \leq \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_\alpha(x) g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)| d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)| \right) \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_\alpha(x)| d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)| \right) \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_\alpha(x)| d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)| \right) \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \|\theta_f x\| = \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)| \right) \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \|x\|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)|} \leq \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)).$$

□

Corollary 2.3. (Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani Uncertainty Principle for 1-Schauder Frames) Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m)$ be 1-Schauder frames for a finite dimensional Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have

$$\|\theta_f x\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(\omega_k)|} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\theta_g x\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g_k(\tau_j)|}.$$

In particular,

$$\|\theta_f x\|_0 \|\theta_g x\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(\omega_k)| \right) \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)}$$

and

$$\|\theta_f x\|_0 + \|\theta_g x\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(\omega_k)|} + \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g_k(\tau_j)|}.$$

REFERENCES

- [1] David L. Donoho and Philip B. Stark. Uncertainty principles and signal recovery. *SIAM J. Appl. Math.*, 49(3):906–931, 1989.

- [2] Michael Elad and Alfred M. Bruckstein. A generalized uncertainty principle and sparse representation in pairs of bases. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 48(9):2558–2567, 2002.
- [3] K. Mahesh Krishna. Functional continuous uncertainty principle. *arXiv:2308.00312v1 [math.FA]* 1 August, 2023.
- [4] K. Mahesh Krishna. Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani uncertainty principle. *arXiv:2304.03324v1 [math.FA]* 5 April, 2023.
- [5] Benjamin Ricaud and Bruno Torrésani. Refined support and entropic uncertainty inequalities. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 59(7):4272–4279, 2013.